

Elizabeth de Burgh as Great Mother Archetype, Queen Archetype and Freedom Archetype in Nigel Tranter's "The Bruce Trilogy"

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Abstract

Elizabeth de Burgh is depicted as a nurturing and supportive mother to her children, particularly her son Robert Bruce. She possesses a maternal instinct that provides emotional support, guidance, and strength to her children through difficult times as the Great Mother Archetype. As a Queen Archetype, she is highlighted by her regal dignity, wisdom, and leadership abilities. Elizabeth's marriage to Robert Bruce and her interactions with the English Court all illustrate her representation of this archetype. Moreover, Elizabeth represents the Freedom Archetype through her unwavering commitment to Scotland's independence. Her active participation in her husband and son's plan for Scottish independence displays her passion for freedom and her willingness to fight for it. Elizabeth de Burgh embodies three archetypes in Nigel Tranter's "The Bruce Trilogy", the Great Mother Archetype, Queen Archetype, and Freedom Archetype. Her character development and actions throughout the plot demonstrate the importance of these archetypes. Her representation of these archetypes shows her as a sanguine, intelligent, talented, safeguarding, complex and multifaceted character, with the ability to be both compassionate and formidable, nurturing and commanding, and loyal to both her family and country. Her character serves as an inspiration for women to embody multiple archetypes and to remain steadfast in their values and beliefs. Hence, this paper traces such evidence of archetypal elements in the trilogy.

Keywords: Elizabeth de Burgh, Great Mother Archetype, Queen Archetype, Freedom Archetype, Nigel Tranter, *The Bruce Trilogy*.

Introduction

Nigel Tranter's "The Bruce Trilogy" is a historical fiction series that delves into the life and times of Robert the Bruce, the Scottish king who famously led his country in the first War of Scottish Independence against England in the late 13th and early 14th centuries. While the trilogy predominantly focuses on the political and military aspects of Bruce's reign, it also features several female characters who play integral roles in the narrative. One of the most prominent women in "The Bruce Trilogy" is Bruce's wife, Elizabeth de Burgh. Elizabeth is portrayed as an intelligent and politically intelligent woman who is instrumental in helping her husband navigate the complex political landscape of medieval Scotland. She is often consulted by Bruce on matters of state and is shown to be a trusted advisor to the king. Despite facing several personal upheavals throughout the course of the trilogy, including the capture of her children and the death of her husband, Elizabeth remains a figure of strength and resilience.

Elizabeth in "The Bruce Trilogy" is an example of strength, intelligence, and resilience in a male-dominated society. Tranter highlights the often-overlooked contributions

of a royal woman in medieval Scotland and provides a nuanced and compelling portrayal of the life of Elizabeth who lived during one of the most tumultuous periods of Scottish history.

M.H. Abrams says about “archetype” in his *The Glossary of Literary Terms*:

...the term archetype denotes recurrent narrative designs, patterns of action, character types, themes and images which are identifiable in a wide variety of works of literature, as well as in myths, dreams, and even social rituals. (15)

According to him, the archetype is a universal symbol that evokes the unconscious responses of a man. It may be about a society or a character or a classical work. Indeed, Plato's idea of beauty and ‘philosopher-king’ (*The Republic*) is the prototype of all archetypal models.

Jung affirms that the artistic process begins with the primordial image or vision of a writer. Primordial images are embedded in the collective unconscious. Jung names it as 'objective psyche' or 'racial memory'. Jung elucidates archetypes as “a priori, inborn form of intuition” (qtd. in Leitch 998). He writes, “The collective unconscious is shaped by the forces of heredity; from it, consciousness has developed” (*Psychology* 183). Feist and Feist argue “Humans inherit a *collective unconscious* that helps shape many of their attitudes...” (133)

Leslie Fiedler in *Love and Death in the American Novel* advocates that archetypes make apparent themselves in their purest form in the myths of culture and literary masterpieces exist when a writer uses archetypes, in his creation.

Maud Bodkin, in her *Archetypal Patterns in Poetry* (1934) applies the major theories of Carl Jung to literature. She analyses how archetypal elements function in literature and overpowers the reader. Bodkin writes about the idea of Jung:

...the stirring in the reader's mind, within or beneath his conscious response, of unconscious forces which he terms as ‘primordial images’, or archetypes. These archetypes he describes as ‘psychic residua of numberless experiences of the same type’, experiences which have happened not to the individual but to his ancestors and of which the results are inherited in the structure of brain, a priorim determinants of individual experience. (Bodkin 1)

Joseph Campbell argues in support of the recurring model of a hero's adventures in the myths of many cultures and created the hero's journey as a 'monomyth' (*The Hero with Thousand Faces*). Most of the ideas of Campbell relate to Jung's theory of collective unconsciousness.

Northrop Frye considers archetypes “as associative clusters which are communicable because a large number of people within the culture are familiar with them” (102) in his *Anatomy of Criticism*. The arguments of the critics support the qualities of archetypes. Whether it may be a man or woman, these qualities work. Elizabeth is a great model of superb archetypal qualities. Her character is touch stoned as the great mother, queen and freedom archetypes from supporting evidence from *The Bruce Trilogy* in the proceeding parts of the article.

As an archetypal character, Elizabeth de Burgh, an influential figure in Scottish history, is often considered the epitome of loyalty, perseverance, courage, and strength. In Nigel Tranter's “The Bruce Trilogy,” Elizabeth de Burgh, the wife of Robert Bruce, not only serves as a loving and supportive partner but also plays a crucial role in shaping the future of Scotland. Her character embodies the archetypal model of a loyal and supportive wife, who stands beside her husband during the good times and the bad, no matter what the cost may be.

From the very beginning of the novel, Elizabeth de Burgh shows immense loyalty and an iron determination to remain at Robert Bruce's side no matter what happens. Despite being in an arranged marriage, Elizabeth falls in love with Robert Bruce and marries him despite the political turmoil that surrounds their union. She stands by him through all the hardships that accompany the endless wars for the Scottish throne. Her constant unwavering support and encouragement towards Robert Bruce make her an essential part of the success of the Bruce dynasty. Elizabeth's major contribution to the success of her dynasty is her ability to inspire and motivate her husband, Robert Bruce, to become a warrior and a leader who eventually unifies a divided Scotland. Elizabeth's perseverance in hard times also makes her an excellent example of an archetypical character. When Robert Bruce is defeated in battle, Elizabeth is the one who motivates him to rise and fight again. Elizabeth remains dedicated to her family's cause. Her perseverance in the face of adversity shines through in her ability to keep fighting for Scottish independence, even when everyone around her doubts its possibility. Elizabeth's courage and strength in the face of danger make her an ardent archetype. She never hesitates to take the hard road when it comes to protecting her family and her country. She risks her life as she accompanies Robert Bruce on his journey to claim the Scottish throne. During the many battles she and her husband fight, Elizabeth shows exceptional courage and strength by leading the Bruce army while Robert Bruce was injured. Her leadership skills are evident in her ability to inspire the Bruce army to victory, which ultimately leads to the end of the War of Independence.

Elizabeth de Burgh embraces archetypical qualities that enforce the values of loyalty, perseverance, courage, and strength. The iconic role of Elizabeth de Burgh in Scottish history as a supportive and zealous wife to Robert Bruce makes her a model character. Elizabeth's dedication to her family's cause and tenacity in the face of adversity make her an iconic role model to many women for generations to come. Elizabeth de Burgh remains an inspiration to society, a shining example of what an ideal woman embodies when it comes to love, loyalty, and leadership.

Elizabeth de Burgh as Great Mother Archetype

Tranter's "The Bruce Trilogy" is a chronicle of one of the most important figures in Scottish history, Robert Bruce. But behind every great man, there is a great woman, and in this case, it is none other than Robert Bruce's wife, Elizabeth de Burgh. Elizabeth de Burgh is a perfect example of the Great Mother archetype as described by Jungian psychology. Her qualities as a nurturing and supportive wife to Robert Bruce, as well as a loving mother, make her a prime example of this archetype.

Scotland, I swear were better without this King! For he is lost, even so. Lost and damned!" "No! No, I say!" Suddenly Elizabeth de Burgh changed. She sat up straight, her eyes blazing, and turning to him gripped his undamaged arm but not tenderly. "You speak like a child. A child sorrowing for itself! This is not the Robert Bruce I wed. I married a man not a brooding, puling bairn! (Book I 348)

Elizabeth de Burgh is first introduced in the book "The Bruce Trilogy" when Robert Bruce is still married to his first wife, Isabella of Mar. Robert and Isabella's relationship has been strained by the fact that they haven't been able to conceive a child, which is essential for Robert's claim to the throne of Scotland. However, when Robert and Isabella's marriage is annulled, he quickly marries Elizabeth de Burgh. Unlike Isabella, Elizabeth can give Robert the son and heir that he needs. Throughout the trilogy, Elizabeth is portrayed as a caring and devoted wife to Robert. She supports him in all his endeavours, whether it's fighting for the

Scottish throne or leading his army into battle. She comforts him when he is grieving the loss of his brothers, and does everything in her power to keep his spirits up. Elizabeth's role as a wife is essential to Robert's success, and it's clear that without her by his side, he wouldn't have been able to achieve all that he did.

He has come to know the Scots. How you ever fight amongst yourselves. So he use you. "Aye. It could be that. But offering so much? You in marriage. Why so much?" "He is a strange man. I believe that he has a true fondness for you. Of a sort. He would bind you to him if he could. If you would play his game, he would cherish you, I think. But you would wholly have to accept his rule of Scotland". "That I will never do. I am Bruce". "He still must believe that he can win you, bribe you, frighten you, hold you. He will work on you, seek to mould you, as a potter moulds his clay. Use you and mould you". "I am no clay to be moulded. I will watch him always. Like a hawk. And seek to use him. Make him win Scotland for me! With your help, my dear. (Book I 255)

But Elizabeth's role as a Great Mother archetype goes beyond just being a supportive wife. She is also a loving mother to her children, particularly her son, David. Throughout the trilogy, Elizabeth is shown to be a doting mother who is fiercely protective of her children. When David is kidnapped by the English and taken to London, Elizabeth does everything in her power to get him back. She even goes to the extent of risking her own life by visiting the English king, Edward II and pleading for her son's release.

Elizabeth's love for her children is an essential part of her role as a Great Mother archetype. She is both nurturing and protective, which are essential qualities of a mother. Her love for her children is also what gives her the strength to support her husband, Robert, in all his endeavours. She knows that everything she does is for the benefit of her children's future, and she is willing to make sacrifices to ensure their safety and happiness. She is a perfect example of the Great Mother archetype as described by Jungian psychology. Her qualities as a nurturing and supportive wife to Robert Bruce, as well as a loving mother, make her a prime example of this archetype. Elizabeth's role in supporting Robert in his quest for the Scottish throne, as well as her love for her children, is what makes her an essential figure in "The Bruce Trilogy." Without her by his side, Robert wouldn't have been able to achieve all that he did. Elizabeth de Burgh might not be the central figure in the trilogy, but she is an essential character whose role as a Great Mother archetype deserves recognition.

Elizabeth de Burgh as Queen Archetype

Elizabeth de Burgh is portrayed as a strong, intelligent, and compassionate queen. She embodies the various qualities of a queen archetype and her character development throughout the trilogy showcases her transformation into a true queen. From the beginning, Elizabeth is depicted as a valuable asset to her husband, Robert Bruce. She is his confidant, advisor, and a strong pillar of support during his trials and tribulations in claiming the Scottish throne. Her loyalty and unwavering dedication to Robert's cause, and by extension, the Scottish people, are evident in her actions, decisions, and words.

The young woman turned her face away a little, so that his lips met only the damp fur-trimmed broadcloth. "My Lord Robert", she objected, "If a woman you so greatly need, perhaps I might even find one for you. There are many at this Court who would serve you willingly, even hotly, I swear! For myself, I am . . . otherwise". "What do you mean? Otherwise?" "I am no . . . serving woman, sir. I am Elizabeth de Burgh". "You think I do not know it, woman? Think you I

would be thus with any other? It is Elizabeth de Burgh I want, have ached and pined for, have dreamed of, sought and awaited. Aye, and prayed for. All these years. You your beauty and proud spirit. Your adorable person and comeliness". He had pushed aside her hood now, and was gasping this into her hair and against her ear, her soft turned cheek. "Aye, your body, girl. But your love, also. Your love, your heart . . ." (Book I 249)

As a queen archetype, Elizabeth also possesses a keen sense of diplomacy and an innate ability to inspire and lead her people. Her rousing speeches and unwavering faith in her husband's leadership serve to rally the Scottish people in their fight for independence. Her diplomatic skills are also evident in her successful negotiations with the English, securing peace for Scotland during a time of war.

It was the Lady Elizabeth de Burgh's turn to clear her throat and she did it in no tentative or apologetic fashion. "These young lords travel in great haste, Father", she interrupted loftily. "That, they made all too clear! It is not for us to hold them back. Moreover, I would not choose this place and company to stand and talk !" Most evidently she disapproved of her righteous indignation being submerged under a masking tide of masculine camaraderie. She turned to her litter again. (Book I 32, 33)

However, Elizabeth's most significant strength lies in her compassion. As a queen archetype, she is the embodiment of the Mother Earth figure who is nurturing, protective, and compassionate towards her people. Elizabeth's concern for the well-being of the Scottish people is evident in her tireless efforts to alleviate their suffering. She sets up hospitals, schools, and orphanages, and ensures that the common folk have access to necessities like food and shelter.

Elizabeth also displays immense strength and resilience in the face of adversity. Her unwavering faith in her husband and her country inspires those around her, especially in moments of doubt. When Robert is defeated in battle, and the future of Scotland looks bleak, Elizabeth refuses to give up hope. She remains steadfast in her belief that Scotland will eventually gain her independence, leading her husband and his army to victory.

My love for you, Robert, I am strong. Strong with your strength. It was your strength that first drew me to you. You are strong still only weary. In pain. Mourning your friends. And alone. As only a king may be alone. But now I am with you again. To restore part of your strength. That I had borrowed in exchange for my heart!" He drew her to him there on the hillock in dight of all. "Quiet you," he said gently. "You have said enough. Done enough. Done it all. I will be strong yes. Strong now. Until one day I give you a whole realm to cherish. Instead of one stumbling man, Elizabeth de Burgh." "to that I will hold you, Robert Bruce," she agreed glad-eyed. "I.. and Saint Fillan!" Hand in hand they turned to face downhill. (Book I 351)

Indeed, Elizabeth de Burgh is a queen archetype who embodies the various qualities that epitomize a strong, intelligent, and compassionate monarch. Her character development throughout the trilogy showcases her transformation from a loyal wife to a queen who inspires, leads, and protects her people.

The Queen and Marjory rode beside Bruce. It was nothing new for Elizabeth de Burgh, daughter of English King Edward's greatest friend, the Earl of Ulster, to be hunted, a fugitive. Since she threw in her lot with Bruce four years before, she

had known little of peace and security in a savaged and war-torn land. But for young Marjory this was her first taste of campaigning. She had been reared in care and seclusion at her dead mother's old home, the remote, strong castle of Kildrummy in Mar. (Book – II 18)

Her unwavering faith in her husband's leadership and her compassion towards the Scottish people make her a vital figure in Scotland's fight for independence.

Elizabeth de Burgh as Freedom Archetype

Elizabeth de Burgh, serves as a powerful symbol of the freedom archetype. Her unwavering support for her husband's cause and her strong will in the face of adversity embody the characteristics of a free spirit, unafraid to fight against oppression and injustice. She was a formidable force in her own right, with a regal bearing that commanded respect from even the most stubborn of foes. She was deeply devoted to her husband's vision for Scotland, believing in his ability to lead his people to independence. Elizabeth's loyalty to her husband is evident from the start of the novel, when she accompanies him on his journey to claim the Scottish throne. Despite facing significant risks to her safety, Elizabeth is unafraid to stand by Robert's side and fight for his cause. Elizabeth continues to demonstrate her fierce independence and strength of character. She proves herself to be a capable leader, often advising her husband on matters of state and politics. She is not content to simply sit back and watch events unfold but takes an active role in shaping the direction of her country.

I would liefer have the man for husband who slew Comyn and defied all Edward's fury, than.. than this weakling!" he groaned. "you say this? You also? God pity me...!" That was a whisper. "Aye, God pity you, Robert Bruce! And me wed to you! And this land, with a faint-heart for King! A broken scepter indeed!" He stiffened. "You are finished?" he asked. "No, I am not. You took that scepter. None thrust it upon you. You are the King now. Crowned and anointed. There is no undoing it, no turning back. So if you are the King, for God's good sake be the King! A weak king is the greatest curse upon a nation." He stared at her biting his lip. "What was it that we did at Scone?" she demanded, her beauty only heightened by her passion. "Was it only a show? Play-acting? Or was it the truth? God's work? Did Abbot Henry save the Stone for nothing? That oil on your brow what was it? A priest's mummer? Or the blessed anointing of God's Holy Spirit upon you? You, only. Which? For if it was truth, then it gave you authority. Above all men. Whatever you have done, you are now God's Anointed. Take that authority. Use it. Wield your sword of state. You have many loyal men still. A whole people still looks to you in hope. Fight on. Avenge Methven. Be Robert the King!" Abruptly her voice broken, and her fiercely upright carriage seemed to crumble. "Oh, Robert be Elizabeth de Burgh's man!" (Book I 348, 349)

In addition to political acumen, Elizabeth is also a skilled negotiator and diplomat. She can navigate the complex relationships between Scotland, England, and other neighbouring countries with ease, leveraging her intelligence and social skills to secure strategic alliances for her husband's cause. Her ability to inspire trust and confidence in those she interacts with is a testament to her strength of character and her commitment to the cause of Scottish independence. She shines as a freedom archetype of her patriotic qualities.

Conclusion

Throughout the novel, Elizabeth serves as a symbol of freedom, both for herself and

for those around her. Her fierce determination to fight against oppression and her unwavering loyalty to her husband's cause inspire those who come into contact with her. Her commitment to the values of justice and equality serve as a beacon of hope for those who would see Scotland rise against the tyranny of English rule. She is a powerful symbol of the Great Mother, Queen and Freedom archetypes in "The Bruce Trilogy." Her unwavering commitment to her husband's cause, her strength of character, and her resolute spirit in the face of adversity make her an inspiration for those seeking to break free from tyranny and oppression. She fought tirelessly for the cause of Scottish independence and her legacy continues to inspire women who strive for freedom and justice in their own lives.

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